

Tiktok Shop: Future of E-Commerce? How Can Galderma Leverage Tiktok Shop to Increase its Penetration and Improve its Market Share in Indonesia Skincare Market?

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ABSTRACT: TikTok was introduced to the Indonesian market in September 2017. Upon its launch, TikTok quickly gained popularity among Indonesian users, especially among the younger demographic, for its short-form video content that allowed for creative expression and entertainment. One of TikTok services is TikTok Shop, an integrated e-commerce capabilities directly within the TikTok app, allowing users to browse, purchase, and sell products without leaving the platform. They launch this service in April 2021. The platform introduced features like shoppable videos and live shopping events, where users could interact with influencers and brands in real-time while purchasing products providing a new and engaging way for Indonesian businesses to reach potential customers and boost sales through interactive and entertaining content.

Galderma Indonesia Healthcare is one of the leading companies dedicated to advancing dermatology for every skin story. Galderma strategically its positioned in attractive, consumer-driven segments of the dermatology market, characterized by high growth fundamentals supported by science-based product differentiation and premium positioning. One of Galderma's brands that is available in Indonesia is Cetaphil.

Cetaphil products are available in modern retailers with Health & Beauty channel as the top contributor, followed by general trade and pharmacy channel. Even though available, Cetaphil is still low in in skincare category penetration.

This study examines the positioning and promotional strategies of Cetaphil on TikTok Shop using qualitative research methods. Primary data was gathered through expert interviews, while secondary data was sourced from internal company reports, previous research studies, and strategic agency reports.

KEYWORDS: Content marketing, e-commerce, Shoppertainment.

INTRODUCTION

The evolution of e-commerce in Indonesia has been marked by rapid growth, driven initially by increased internet penetration, smartphone adoption, and the rise of major platforms such as Tokopedia, Bukalapak, and Shopee around 2015. This pre-pandemic growth was bolstered by significant investments from local unicorns like Gojek and Traveloka. However, the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 acted as a catalyst for accelerated digital adoption, particularly as consumers in smaller cities turned to online shopping amidst lockdowns and social distancing measures. The pandemic also spurred the expansion of digital payment systems and logistics networks to meet rising e-commerce demands. Post-pandemic, the sector continues to grow, with market projections indicating an increase from USD 52.93 billion in 2023 to USD 86.81 billion by 2028. The increasing integration of social media platforms, particularly TikTok, has been instrumental in driving social commerce, particularly in the beauty and skincare sectors, where influencer-driven content significantly impacts consumer behavior.

Within this context, the Indonesian skincare market has experienced notable growth, driven by rising consumer awareness and increased disposable incomes. The market was valued at \$2.03 billion in 2021 and is expected to reach \$3.09 billion by 2028, with a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 6.2%. Cetaphil, a leading brand in the derma skincare segment, holds a 65% market share with 50% penetration, though its presence in the broader skincare market remains limited at 1.2%. This underscores its strength in specialized segments but also highlights opportunities for broader expansion. As Generation Z increasingly relies on e-commerce platforms such as TikTok and Instagram for product discovery, brands must adapt to capitalize on the shift towards social commerce.

TikTok Shop has emerged as a key player in this trend, leveraging its algorithmic approach and influencer-driven marketing to enhance engagement and drive consumer purchases. This study seeks to provide strategic recommendations for strengthening Galderma's competitive positioning in the Indonesian skincare market by utilizing the rapid growth of TikTok Shop.

1. Theoretical Foundation

1.1.1 Segmentation, Targeting, Positioning (STP)

Philip Kotler's STP (Segmentation, Targeting, and Positioning) framework is a strategic marketing approach that enables businesses to identify, target, and effectively position their offerings to serve specific consumer groups. This approach involves segmenting a broader market into smaller, homogenous groups, selecting the most promising segments to target, and positioning the brand or product in a way that resonates with the chosen audience (Kotler & Keller, 2016).

Segmentation divides the market into distinct groups based on factors such as demographics, geography, psychographics, and behavior. This helps marketers tailor strategies to specific needs. **Targeting** involves evaluating and selecting segments based on their potential profitability and alignment with the company's objectives. Company may adopt one of four strategies: undifferentiated (mass) marketing, differentiated marketing, concentrated (niche) marketing, or micromarketing. **Positioning** is the process of creating a distinct brand identity in the target segment's mind, often through a unique value proposition. Effective positioning integrates with the marketing mix (product, price, place, promotion) to ensure the brand's image is consistently communicated across all marketing efforts.

1.1.2 Marketing Mix

The marketing mix, as outlined by McCarthy and expanded upon by Kotler, consists of four key elements—product, price, place, and promotion—commonly referred to as the "four Ps" of marketing. These components provide a structured framework for businesses to develop and execute marketing strategies tailored to market demands, thereby maintaining a competitive advantage (Kotler & Keller, 2016).

Product represents the goods or services a business offers, encompassing the total value proposition, including design, functionality, quality, and branding. Effective product strategies focus on innovation and differentiation to meet consumer needs and create a unique market position. **Price** is a critical component that influences profitability and market positioning. Pricing strategies should reflect the product's perceived value and adapt to market conditions through dynamic, penetration, or value-based pricing. **Place** refers to the distribution channels that ensure the product is accessible to the target market, with emphasis on optimizing logistics and supply chains. Efficient placement enhances customer convenience and satisfaction. **Promotion** involves the communication strategies used to inform and persuade consumers about the product's value. Integrated marketing communications help ensure consistent brand messaging across platforms, leveraging data-driven insights to engage the target audience effectively and increase conversion rates.

1.1.3 Content Marketing and Social Commerce

Content marketing involves the strategic creation and distribution of valuable, relevant, and consistent content aimed at attracting and engaging a specific target audience to drive profitable customer action. The content marketing approach can be categorized into four objectives: entertain, inspire, educate, and convince. **Entertain** focuses on creating light, engaging content like viral videos or quizzes, which increases brand awareness through emotional connections and shareability. **Inspire** seeks to motivate the audience with aspirational content such as customer success stories or lifestyle blogs, fostering a deeper emotional bond by aligning with consumer values. **Educate** aims to provide valuable knowledge, positioning the brand as an authority with resources like e-books, webinars, or guides, promoting intellectual engagement and building trust. **Convince** involves persuasive content like product demonstrations and testimonials, designed to lead consumers toward purchase decisions through rational arguments and clear calls-to-action.

In the context of social commerce, platforms such as TikTok Shop integrate these content marketing strategies by combining user-generated content, influencer partnerships, and algorithmic recommendations. This allows for a seamless shopping experience where users can discover, evaluate, and purchase products within the app. Academic literature suggests that social commerce creates more interactive and personalized shopping experiences, enhancing engagement and profitability for businesses (Huang & Benyoucef, 2013). Content marketing, particularly in video format, is regarded as a powerful tool for enhancing brand visibility and driving

business growth (Content Marketing Institute, 2015). The Content Marketing Matrix, introduced by Smart Insights, helps businesses evaluate and guide content strategies based on these key objectives: entertain, inspire, educate, and convince.

1.2 Conceptual Framework

The objective of a conceptual framework is to categorize and describe key concepts relevant to a study while mapping the relationships between them. By incorporating both theoretical perspectives and empirical research, the framework helps to organize and clarify the concepts, revealing areas of overlap, contradiction, and refinement (Rocco & Plakhotnik, 2009). In essence, a conceptual framework is derived from existing concepts and serves to construct the researcher's perspective on the issue under investigation.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework, Amri (2024)

2. Research Methodology

2.1 Research Design

The completion of this research involves following a structured process to develop a new strategic framework for Galderma Indonesia. The study employs a qualitative research methodology, which often relies on a single data collection method, such as semi-structured interviews, paired with corresponding qualitative analytical procedures (Saunders et al., 2020). This approach allows for an in-depth exploration of the subject matter to inform the development of the strategic framework.

2.2 Data Collection Method

2.2.1 Primary Data

To obtain primary data, questionnaire followed by series of an in-depth interview will be conducted with key stakeholders within Galderma as well as external participants who are closely related to the industry. These interviews aim to gather in-depth information and insights that are critical to understanding the relevant market dynamics, strategic considerations, and challenges faced by Galderma.

2.2.2 Secondary Data

Secondary data refers to information that has been previously collected and documented in research studies, reports from marketing agencies, or other established sources where author can access these data through various work-related channels. Utilizing secondary data offers several advantages, including the reduction of time and costs associated with primary data collection, and the availability

of large and diverse datasets. Furthermore, secondary data can be valuable for extending previous research, facilitating comparisons across studies, and analyzing trends or patterns over time, thus enriching the overall research process.

2.3 Data Analysis Methods

This research uses content analysis to analyze qualitative data, drawn from participants' personal expressions, behavioral observations, and recorded interactions. Content analysis systematically examines common phrases, words, and patterns of expression to identify themes and relationships, providing a qualitative understanding of participant perspectives (Schindler, 2021). While content analysis offers a structured approach to analyzing textual data, the study also utilizes a Causal Loop Diagram (CLD) to visually represent cause-and-effect relationships within a system.

Based on systems thinking theory, CLD illustrates the interdependencies and feedback loops within complex systems. This approach, as emphasized by Forrester (1961), highlights how individual components of a system interact to create cyclical patterns of influence. Arrows in CLDs depict directional cause-and-effect relationships, helping to identify feedback loops that either reinforce or balance system behavior. This method depersonalizes problem identification by focusing on system behaviors rather than individuals, offering insights into leverage points for change within the system.

3. Results

3.1 Business Issue Analysis

Although Cetaphil holds a dominant position in the derma skincare segment, its limited penetration in the broader skincare market indicates that its current segmentation and targeting strategies may be overly concentrated on a niche consumer base. To enhance market penetration, Cetaphil should reevaluate its segmentation approach, identifying wider consumer groups with general skincare needs and expanding its reach beyond its core audience. This strategic shift could enable the brand to tap into a broader market and address a wider range of skincare preferences.

3.1.1 Segmentation

Demographic Segmentation: Cetaphil primarily targets consumers with sensitive skin, spanning a broad demographic range but skewing toward middle-to-upper income individuals who can afford premium skincare products. The brand also appeals to urban, highly educated populations who are more aware of dermatologically tested products.

Geographic Segmentation: Cetaphil focuses on major urban centers such as Jakarta, Surabaya, and Bandung, where higher disposable incomes and greater access to premium products make these markets more attractive. Urban populations, exposed to global trends and brands, are key targets for Cetaphil's marketing efforts.

Psychographic Segmentation: Cetaphil appeals to health-conscious consumers who prioritize wellness and are mindful of skincare ingredients. These consumers prefer products with minimal, safe ingredients and are drawn to clinically proven, dermatologist-recommended solutions that avoid harsh chemicals.

Behavioral Segmentation: Cetaphil segments its market based on consumer behaviors, targeting both those seeking products for daily skincare routines and those with chronic skin conditions like eczema or acne. The brand also appeals to consumers who rely on expert recommendations, particularly from dermatologists or medical professionals.

3.1.2 Targeting

Cetaphil's marketing strategy has primarily employed a niche approach, targeting consumers with sensitive skin or dermatological conditions such as eczema, acne, or rosacea. Its positioning as a dermatologically tested, clinically validated skincare brand appeals to this specific segment, which values product safety, efficacy, and endorsements from medical professionals. Cetaphil has built strong brand loyalty within this niche by emphasizing its mild, non-irritating formulations and minimal ingredients, reinforced by recommendations from healthcare professionals.

However, this niche focus presents several challenges. First, the limited market size restricts growth potential as Cetaphil primarily targets a specialized segment. Second, broader market awareness is constrained, as consumers without sensitive skin may be less familiar with the brand. Additionally, competition within this niche is high, with brands like La Roche Posay, CeraVe, and Bioderma vying for the same consumer base, requiring Cetaphil to constantly innovate. Lastly, expanding beyond the niche to attract a broader audience can dilute the brand's identity and risk alienating its core consumer base. These factors necessitate strategic adjustments to balance niche loyalty with broader market expansion.

3.1.3 Positioning

Cetaphil’s positioning strategy focuses on establishing itself as a trusted, dermatologist-recommended brand designed for individuals with sensitive skin or specific dermatological conditions. The brand differentiates itself by emphasizing dermatological credibility and skin sensitivity, positioning its products as gentle, non-irritating, and safe, free from harsh chemicals. This benefit-based positioning sets Cetaphil apart from more cosmetic-focused skincare brands, as it highlights clinically tested, scientifically backed solutions.

Cetaphil primarily targets urban, middle-to-upper income consumers and individuals with specific dermatological needs, a demographic that values professional endorsements and proven efficacy. By emphasizing its dermatologist-recommended and clinically validated nature, Cetaphil strengthens its credibility and appeals to consumers seeking reliable, medically supported skincare products.

3.2 Content Analysis

A questionnaire followed by in-depth interviews with participants offered valuable insights for this study. The interview data were analyzed using content analysis, focusing on identifying the frequency and occurrence of key elements. These elements were categorized under the Segmentation, Targeting, and Positioning (STP) framework and the Content Marketing approach. This analysis yielded a comprehensive understanding of potential strategic actions to leverage TikTok Shop, aiming to increase Cetaphil’s market penetration and strengthen its positioning in Indonesia’s skincare market.

Table 4.1 Content Analysis from Primary Data Collection

Category	Insights
Indonesia skincare market	Big, dynamic, and is still developing (huge potential). More brands are coming tapped in into premium segments.
	Key trends: innovative, health-conscious consumers, sensitive-skin expert.
Purchase decision in digital platform	Influencer endorsements, reviews on product features, value and price relevancy, ease of purchase, livestream.
TikTok Shop impact on skincare market in Indonesia	Reshaping consumer behavior, blend entertainment with shopping, high engagement rates, short video format, penetrating younger generation.
	Competitors are actively use TikTok to showcase their high efficacy.
STP	Gen Z, millennials, urban high purchasing power, dermatologist-recommended, advanced technology, superior product features, sensitive skin.
Content marketing	Entertain, followed by educate, convince, and inspire.
	Engaging fun content to capture attention and share inspiring success stories to build emotional connections.
	Edutainment type of a content to promote Cetaphil differentiation compared to mass brands.
	Science and innovation behind the brand while providing proof to convince consumers on the claim.
Influencers’ role in shaping consumer perception	Credible source to create honest review, able to translate scientific terms into everyday sentences, drive impulse purchase.
	Crucial, truth and real advocacy.
TikTok interactive features	Engaging livestream, and user-generated content (UGC).
	Smooth and engaging shopping experience, discover and purchase directly within the app.
	360-degree communications on the brand multiple touch points.
	Interactive platform between brand and relevant audience.
	More advanced competition (content and claim wise).

Potential challenge when leveraging TikTok Shop	Multi-platform engagement, multi-type of influencers. Right investment.
Future technological trends	Augmented reality (AR), artificial intelligence (AI) for skin check.
Critical factors that will determine success on TikTok Shop	Creating relevant and engaging content, heavy education through livestreaming, deep dive data and algorithm to create end to end consumer journey, and right investments.

3.3 Causal Loop Diagram

Causal Loop Diagrams (CLDs) are a key tool for visualizing and understanding the complexity of systems by illustrating the relationships and feedback loops between variables (McGlashan et al., 2016). CLDs are used in systems thinking to depict how elements within a system interact, forming either reinforcing or balancing feedback loops that drive system behavior.

1. Reinforcing Loop: A reinforcing loop, or positive feedback loop, amplifies changes within a system, leading to exponential growth or decline. In this study, increasing Cetaphil's engagement in social commerce enhances brand equity among Gen Z consumers, which, in turn, increases market penetration. As penetration grows, further investments in influencer-driven content marketing reinforce this cycle, creating continuous growth for the brand. This reinforcing loop is illustrated as: more social commerce → higher brand equity → increased penetration → more social engagement, forming a self-reinforcing cycle.
2. Balancing Loop (B): A balancing loop, or negative feedback loop, works to stabilize the system by counteracting changes. In Cetaphil's case, reliance on offline retail channels limits digital engagement, reducing online penetration. This can hinder growth in the online market. However, recognizing this imbalance may lead Cetaphil to reallocate resources toward social commerce, thereby balancing its offline and online strategies. This loop can be described as: more offline channel focus → reduced digital engagement → lower online penetration → shift toward online channels to restore balance.

Figure 4.1 Casual Loop Diagram Cetaphil X TikTok Shop, Amri (2024)

Reinforcing Loop (R1): Offline Channel and Low Penetration

1. Strong presence in offline channel → + → Dependency on offline channel
2. Dependency on offline channel → - → Digital engagement
3. Digital Engagement → - → Market Penetration

Balancing Loop (B1): Shifting Consumer Behavior

1. Consumer shift to online → + → Social commerce utilization
2. Social commerce utilization → + → Increased market penetration
3. Increased market penetration → - → Dependency on offline channel
4. Dependency on offline channel → + → Digital engagement (this could balance the loop if more resources are allocated to online channels)

Reinforcing Loop (R2): Social Commerce and Brand Equity

1. Social commerce → + → Brand equity among Gen Z
2. Brand equity among Gen Z → + → Increased market penetration
3. Increased market penetration → + → Interactive content marketing
4. Interactive content marketing → + → Digital engagement
5. Digital engagement → + → Seamless shopping entertainment integration (TikTok Shop)

4.4 Business Solutions

Cetaphil, currently experiencing low penetration in the broader skincare market, must recalibrate its strategies to enhance growth and market reach. A critical component of this recalibration involves targeting Gen Z, a demographic that plays a significant role in shaping skincare trends and is highly engaged with social commerce platforms such as TikTok and Instagram. Gen Z consumers prioritize peer recommendations and viral content over traditional advertising, making platforms like TikTok Shop ideal for reaching this audience.

By expanding its segmentation to include Gen Z and leveraging influencer marketing and user-generated content, Cetaphil can capitalize on the viral nature of social commerce and align with Gen Z's purchasing behaviors. This strategic approach would allow Cetaphil to strengthen its brand positioning by blending its dermatological credibility with social media relevance. Given Gen Z's projected global spending growth of \$2.7 trillion over the next six years, capturing their attention today is crucial for securing future market dominance. By adapting its marketing efforts and refining its segmentation, Cetaphil can transition from niche market leadership to broader industry penetration, ensuring sustainable growth and long-term brand loyalty in the competitive skincare market.

4.4.1 Content Marketing

To increase market penetration and appeal to a broader audience, particularly Gen Z, Cetaphil should adopt a content marketing strategy that balances the pillars of entertainment, inspiration, education, and persuasion. This approach will align with Gen Z's digital behaviors and values while maintaining Cetaphil's dermatological credibility.

Entertain: Gen Z prioritizes engaging and relatable content. Cetaphil can create short-form videos on platforms like TikTok, using trending music, viral challenges, or humorous skincare routines to capture attention. For example, a TikTok challenge where users share skincare "fails" followed by solutions using Cetaphil products would showcase the brand's personality while fitting seamlessly into Gen Z's consumption habits.

Inspire: User-generated content (UGC) and influencer collaborations are key to inspiring Gen Z. Campaigns encouraging users to share their skincare journeys with Cetaphil can foster authenticity and community engagement. Collaborating with influencers who represent Gen Z's diversity—such as skin positivity advocates or eco-conscious voices—can further enhance Cetaphil's inspirational messaging, focusing on themes like skin confidence and self-care.

Educate: Given its dermatological credibility, Cetaphil can leverage educational content to explain skincare science in an accessible way. Tutorials, dermatologist Q&A sessions, or myth-busting videos about skincare misconceptions are ideal for platforms like Instagram and TikTok. These efforts will help build trust with Gen Z, who value informed decision-making and reliable sources.

Convince: To persuade Gen Z to purchase Cetaphil products, showcasing testimonials from real users, influencers, and dermatologists is essential. Social proof, such as before-and-after transformations and honest reviews, will resonate with Gen Z's preference for authentic peer recommendations. Highlighting how Cetaphil products align with sustainable skincare or clean beauty trends can further enhance its appeal.

4.4.2 Interactive Shopping Experience

Cetaphil could enhance consumer engagement by launching a user-generated content (UGC) campaign, such as the #CetaphilSkinJourney challenge, encouraging customers to share their skincare experiences using Cetaphil products. This campaign would allow users to post videos or photos detailing their personal skin transformations, with product tags or links enabling viewers to make direct purchases from the posts. This seamless integration allows potential buyers to observe the products in real-time and make informed purchasing decisions without leaving the app.

Additionally, Cetaphil can collaborate with influencers or dermatologists to host live events on platforms like TikTok Shop. During these livestreams, the hosts could demonstrate full skincare routines with Cetaphil products while interacting with viewers through live chats. Special deals or discounts offered during the livestream could further incentivize immediate purchases, creating an engaging experience that combines real-time demonstrations with instant conversions.

Rather than relying solely on discounts, Cetaphil should focus on creating content that brings its products to life, allowing consumers to experience their value. On content-driven platforms, content that demonstrates the practical benefits of a product has a greater influence on purchasing decisions than discounts alone. To capture Gen Z's attention, Cetaphil should use content that resonates across the consumer decision journey, from initial interest to evaluation and final purchase.

Three key content attributes—emotional resonance, authentic expression, and relatable realism—are essential for influencing consumer decisions. Emotional resonance is achieved by presenting the product's value in aspirational ways, aligning the product with desirable lifestyles. Authentic expression is conveyed through credible, genuine experiences shared by key opinion leaders (KOLs) or influencers, who build trust through personal use and honest reviews. Relatable realism involves showcasing the product in real-world settings, enabling consumers to visualize its benefits in their own lives. These strategies empower consumers to make confident, informed decisions without needing additional research, ultimately driving increased engagement and conversions for Cetaphil.

4.4.3 Shoppertainment

Shoppertainment, a blend of shopping and entertainment, integrates engaging content and interactive experiences into the retail process to create an immersive and enjoyable shopping environment. This concept, especially prevalent in digital and social commerce, reflects consumers' growing preference for experiential shopping. By combining entertainment with the convenience of e-commerce, shoppertainment captures attention, drives engagement, and influences purchasing behavior.

According to a leading beauty company's Head of Ecommerce in Indonesia, established brands can no longer afford to ignore the rapid growth of shoppertainment. The risk extends beyond losing market share to missing opportunities for creating meaningful consumer connections. The foundation for success in shoppertainment involves three key shifts: content-centricity, full-funnel optimization, and leveraging the creator ecosystem. First, consumers are increasingly valuing content that reveals product value over impulsive, discount-based purchases. Second, content is expected to enhance the shopping experience by facilitating seamless transitions from browsing to buying. Third, community-driven content platforms, such as TikTok, are becoming central to brand discovery.

TikTok has become a hub for content-driven shopping, where consumers discover new brands and products through a mix of regular and branded content. Its platform not only facilitates content-triggered shopping but also enables convenient on-platform transactions through shoppable content, live shopping, and embedded buying links. According to the Head of Ecommerce, investing in TikTok Shop fuels growth across all channels, making it a pivotal touchpoint for brand discovery and influencing broader consumer purchasing behaviors across the retail ecosystem.

4.5 Creating a Shoppertainment Framework

In TikTok Shop, the term "persona" refers to the ideal customer profile, encompassing specific behaviors, preferences, and demographics that brands target on the platform. Understanding this persona allows brands like Cetaphil to tailor their content, marketing strategies, and shopping experiences to align with TikTok's unique combination of social media and e-commerce.

For example, a typical persona on TikTok Shop might include Indonesian males and females born between 1983 and 2001, active on social media, with a simple, fun, and timeless personality. These consumers prioritize high-quality products and enjoyable shopping experiences, are flexible with payment options, and frequently review products before purchasing, particularly in categories like fashion, skincare, and accessories. By identifying and targeting such personas, Cetaphil can optimize its product offerings, content, and engagement strategies to effectively connect with its audience on TikTok Shop.

4.5.1 Product Assortment

Product assortment refers to the variety and range of products offered by sellers or brands on platforms like TikTok Shop, tailored to appeal to TikTok's diverse user base, known as TikTok Persona. This assortment includes a mix of product categories, brands, sizes, and price points, designed to engage TikTok users based on their preferences, behaviors, and trends.

The product assortment on TikTok is largely shaped by user-generated content, influencer marketing, and trending demand. Brands frequently update their offerings to align with viral challenges, seasonal interests, and popular trends on the platform. Influencers play a crucial role in shaping product assortments by curating collections and promoting specific items in their content. Collaborative efforts between brands and influencers further enhance product visibility, encouraging viewers to explore the range of offerings linked to influencer-driven videos. A detailed analysis of product assortment helps assess whether the products offered are optimized to attract consumers and facilitate easy product discovery.

Figure 4.2 Product Assortment Matrix, Amri (2024)

4.5.2 Content

TikTok content consists of short-form videos, typically 15 seconds to 3 minutes long, known for their dynamic, interactive nature that revolves around trends, challenges, music, and viral moments. Creativity and engagement are central to TikTok's content

strategy. This section explores how to create relevant content that captures user attention, engages them during livestreams, and balances branded content with affiliate content.

TikTok creators are individuals who produce engaging videos using music, challenges, tutorials, or personal stories to entertain, educate, or inform their audience. Effective content creation on TikTok requires an understanding of optimal video structure and timing to maximize engagement. A successful video can be structured into four key components:

1. Trouble (5 seconds): Introducing a real-life scene or pain point.
2. Problem Solution (7 seconds): Presenting the product’s benefits, recommendations, and offers.
3. Plot Reversal (5 seconds): Reinforcing the product’s selling points with a call to action.
4. Surprise (5 seconds): Concluding with an impactful effect, promotion, or call to action.

Many TikTok creators focus on specific niches, such as fashion, beauty, fitness, or education, allowing them to connect with targeted audiences and establish authority in those areas. Consistency is crucial for creators, as maintaining a regular posting schedule helps to build a loyal following and remain visible on the platform’s For You Page (FYP). Through these strategies, content creators can effectively engage audiences while aligning with broader marketing goals.

Figure 4.3 Type of Content Creator, Amri (2024)

TikTok content creators engage actively with their audiences by responding to comments, participating in duets, and reacting to viewer feedback, fostering a strong sense of community, and encouraging further interaction. Creators can monetize their content through brand partnerships, affiliate marketing, and live streaming.

Live streaming on TikTok allows users to broadcast real-time videos, interact with viewers through comments, and receive virtual gifts. TikTok Live is frequently used by creators, influencers, and brands for direct engagement and is characterized by its authenticity, making it more relatable and trustworthy for viewers. Live streaming has also become a key component of social commerce, often referred to as shoppertainment, where hosts showcase products in real time, allowing viewers to make instant purchases through embedded links without leaving the stream.

TikTok Live streams have the potential to reach a wider audience beyond existing followers, as the platform’s For You Page (FYP) algorithm can amplify streams that attract significant engagement, potentially making them go viral. Additionally, TikTok affiliators participate in affiliate marketing by promoting products or services on the platform in exchange for commissions on sales generated through their referral links or discount codes. These affiliators leverage their content creation skills and audience influence to drive product discovery and boost sales.

4.5.3 Enable

In this context, "enabling" refers to a brand's capacity to efficiently engage consumers through advertising and marketing, fostering agility and a test-and-learn approach to drive market speed. Expanding audience reach and increasing purchase intent on TikTok can be effectively achieved using a full-funnel advertising strategy, which aligns with the user journey. This strategy guides potential consumers through each stage of the purchase process with targeted ads, enhancing engagement and promoting a more seamless path to conversion.

TikTok offers four key types of ads: in-feed ads, product shopping ads (PSA), video shopping ads (VSA), and live shopping ads (LSA), each designed to engage users in unique ways.

1. In-feed ads appear natively within a user's For You Page (FYP) as they scroll, blending with organic content. These short-form, engaging ads often include interactive calls-to-action (CTAs) like "Shop Now" or "Learn More," encouraging immediate engagement. Designed to mimic the visual style of TikTok, they feel more natural and less intrusive than traditional ads.
2. Product shopping ads (PSA) promote products directly within TikTok, enabling users to discover, interact with, and buy products without leaving the app. These ads are highly engaging, visually dynamic, and often incorporate TikTok trends or influencers, merging entertainment with shopping in a seamless manner.
3. Video shopping ads (VSA) combine TikTok's short-form video format with embedded shopping functionality, allowing users to purchase products directly from the app. These ads typically showcase products within creative contexts, such as tutorials or lifestyle videos, making the shopping experience feel organic and enhancing consumer trust.
4. Live shopping ads (LSA) are used during TikTok Shop's live shopping events, combining real-time interaction with product demonstrations and seamless purchasing. These ads create an immersive shopping experience, offering exclusive deals or limited-time discounts to foster urgency and engagement. Through live interactions, brands can provide instant feedback, answer questions, and guide consumers through the purchasing process, driving immediate sales.

Figure 4.4 Enabling User Journey in TikTok Shop, Amri (2024)

Based on the preceding explanation, a structured framework can be developed to guide Cetaphil's adoption of shoppertainment on TikTok. This framework provides a step-by-step approach for strategically engaging consumers through TikTok Shop by leveraging the platform's unique features. A central element of this framework is identifying the target Persona, which informs decisions related to Product Assortment, Content Creation, and Enable strategies. By understanding the Persona, Cetaphil can tailor its product offerings, create compelling content, and optimize its overall strategy to enhance consumer engagement and drive conversions on TikTok Shop.

Figure 4.5 Shoppertainment Framework, Amri (2024)

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

5.1 Conclusion

This study has made significant progress in addressing how Galderma can leverage TikTok Shop to enhance its penetration and market share in Indonesia's skincare market. By analyzing market trends, consumer behavior, and TikTok's platform characteristics, the research has demonstrated how content influences consumer behavior using the Product Assortment, Content, and Enabling (PCE) framework.

Galderma can strategically drive growth in the evolving digital landscape by optimizing content-driven consumer engagement, fostering influencer partnerships, and creating interactive, seamless shopping experiences (shoppertainment). These strategies position Galderma for success in the dynamic social commerce environment.

Figure 5.1 Shoppertainment Framework, Amri (2024)

5.2 Recommendation

The next major opportunity in commerce focuses on re-engaging consumers by prioritizing their emotional needs through shoppertainment, which emphasizes content-driven commerce that entertains and educates. This approach strengthens brand-consumer connections across various business models, including marketplaces, direct-to-consumer platforms, and TikTok Shop.

Commerce on TikTok stands out in two ways. First, Cetaphil can adopt an entertainment-first strategy aligned with TikTok Shop’s mission to inspire creativity and bring joy. With over 1 billion users engaging on the For You Page (FYP), TikTok content not only entertains but also drives purchasing decisions. Second, the democratization of content creation has empowered users to participate in interest-based communities, creating new centers of influence that shape consumer behavior.

5.3 Future Suggestion

While the study provides clear strategies for penetrating new markets, further research is required to explore deeper consumer insights and the potential of emerging technologies like Augmented Reality (AR). As AR technology evolves, its application in personalized skincare on TikTok could extend beyond basic skin checks to offer tailored product recommendations and interactive skincare routines. This would enhance consumer engagement and provide a more personalized shopping experience, creating new opportunities for growth and market differentiation.

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